

ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF MULTI-STOREY BUILDING USING ETABS

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Abstract: A multi-storey building has several floors at different levels above the ground. Analysis and design of multi-storied building deals with economic factor, serviceability and durability of a building. The foremost basic in structural engineering is the design of simple basic components and members of the building i.e., beams, columns, slabs and footings. This project work aims to analysis and design of a four storied building using ETABS.

ETABS stands for Extended Three-Dimensional Analysis of Building Systems. It is a stand-alone structural analysis programme with a special purpose features for structural design and analysis of building systems. It is simple to use and user friendly and it is unique in its ability to address the full spectrum of tasks involved in the process of structural analysis and design. The main purpose of this software is to design multi-storey building in a systematic process. This project accomplishes a typical design project which is designed as per Indian Codes IS1893-Part 2:2000 and IS456:2000. The design involves determining the most suitable proportions of a structure and dimensioning and detailing the structural elements. Once the structure is analysed and designed it must have sufficient strength to withstand the maximum stresses to which it is subjected. This paper discuss the analysis of a conventional building (G+4) under the effect of shear forces and bending moment of beams and columns.

Keywords: *ETABS, analysis, structural design, shear force, bending moment*

1. Introduction

This Project is based on the analysis and design of a four storied building. The determination of general shape, specific dimension and size of a building is known as structure analysis, so that it will perform the function for it and will safely withstand the influences which will act on throughout its useful life. In short, the specification of the required structure is the most important thing to decide many aspects of the structure, such as functional safety and economic aspects. The entire process of structural planning and designing requires not only imagination and calculations, but also science knowledge of Structural Engineer. In this Project, an effort made on planning, analysis and design of residential building using E-TABS. We have taken a plan of a building on the basis of which the analysis will be done for the whole structure. For the analysis of a building one has to consider all the possible loadings and see that the structure is safe against all possible loading conditions. The dead load and live loads are calculated and applied and the design for beams, columns, footing and slabs are obtained. Analysis of beams and columns has been done using E-TABS software.

2. Significance of The Study

Analysis of a building means the estimation of the response of structures towards variable external loads considering all the deviants that may occur. During the preliminary design-stage the estimated

external load is used to design the size and geometry of the structures of interconnected members by using local building code and specifications of the area where the structure is located. Therefore, assuring the structural integrity, durability etc. Neglecting this crucial analysis and design stage or erring during the process will result in catastrophic failure within the building structure which can, in the worst-case scenario may lead to the loss of lives. Since this stage is the most important, the margin of error is required to be close to zero. We are making use of a software called ETABS, which is a highly efficient structural analysis and design programme consisting of modelling tools, code-based load prescriptions, analysis methods and solution techniques. Through this study we want to signify the importance of analysing and design of a multi-storey building to ensure that it satisfies the safety and serviceability requirements with help of the software ETABS.

3. Review Of Related Studies

Balaji.U and Selvarasan (2016) used ETABS to analyse and design a multi-storeyed building which was under static and dynamic loading. In the study a G+13 storey residential building was studied for earthquake loads using ETABS. Here they assumed that the material property to be linear, static and dynamic analysis were performed. The non-linear analysis was performed by considering severe seismic zones and the behaviour

was assessed by considering type II soil condition. Various results like displacements, base shear were plotted and studied.

Geethu (2016) carried out a comparative study on analysis and design of a multi-storeyed building by STAAD.Pro and ETABS software's. They concluded that while comparing both the results, ETABS software shows higher values of bending moment and axial force

Mr.Raghunandan M and Mrs. Suma Devi (2107) used ETABS non-linear software for simulation of adjacent multi-storeyed RC frame buildings of 15 storey and 10 storey. The provisions which may reduce the effects of pounding like the separation distance, addition of shear walls, lateral bracings and variation in storey height of the buildings have been considered for analysis. The results by considering both fixed and base isolated conditions were arrived.

Mr. Abhayguleria (2016) pointed out that ETABS is commonly used to analyse: skyscrapers, parking, garages, steel & concrete structures, low and high-rise buildings and portal frame structures. The case study in this paper mainly focuses on structural behaviour of a multi-storey building for different plan configurations like rectangular, C, L and I-shape. Modelling of 15- storey RC framed building is done on the ETABS software for analysis. Post analysis of the structure, maximum shear forces, bending moments, and maximum storey displacement are computed and then compared for all the analysed cases.

4.Objectives Of The Study

- To analyze the G+4 building using the software ETABS.
- To design the building for stability, serviceability and also it must be economical.

5.Hypotheses Of The Study

- Awareness on healthy dietary habits among prospective teachers are moderate.
- There is no significant difference between prospective teachers in their awareness on healthy dietary habits with reference to the following background variables.

(i)Gender (ii)Locality of residence (iii)Nature of college (iv)Type of family (v)Medium of Instruction

- There is no significant difference among prospective teachers in their healthy dietary habits with reference to father's and mother's educational qualification

6.Methodology

6.1 Project details

Safe bearing capacity of soil (SBC) = 200KN/mm²

Total height of the building = 15.5m

An already existing G+4 building of plan 15m×20m is considered. It is situated in zone II. The soil condition is medium. The overall height of the building is 15.5m with basement height of 3.5m and the typical floor height is 3m. the building consists of columns of size 230mm×500mm and beams 230mm×450mm respectively. The plan of the column is as shown in the fig.6.1 and the corresponding elevation in fig.6.2

Fig 6.1.1 Column layout of the building(plan)

Fig 6.1.2 Building Frame

6.2 Modelling

Step 1: New Model

- Press (File and choose New Model)
- Choose the following settings.
- Design the (Grid Only) according to the plan of beams (Spacing method). Fill the Uniform grid spacing.

Step 2: Defining the Material Properties

- Defining the materials type like concrete, steel, rebar and masonry with their standard grade.

Step 3: Defining the Sectional Property

- Defining the column properties.

In this plan we take concrete grade as M25 for the ground floor as well as for the upper stories.

Step 4: Defining Beam Properties.

In this modelling we can take M25 concrete for the Ground Floor as well as for the upper stories.

Step 5: Defining the Slab Properties.

Step 6: Assigning all the elements to the model.

3D View of the Building

Fig 6.6 Three-dimensional view of the building

We can define the various load according to IS codes specified.

Fig7.4(c) 3-Dimensional View

Step 8: After assigning all the loads replicate the floors(G+4). We did diaphragm for the plan.

Step 9: Analyze the building.

- After the load application, we analyze the structure.
- The bending moment of the whole building is shown in

Max Bending Moment for Beams and column

Step 7: Defining and assigning the loads

Maximum bending moment value for beams and column

Frames	Bending moment values KN-m	
	Column	Beam
X-Direction		
A and E	30.25	29.192
B and D	31.89	20.91
C	30.57	20.4
Y-Direction		
1 and 4	24.73	18.27
2 and 3	25.86	18.81

Based on the above BM values we designed manually for Beams and Columns.

As per the design, the dimensions of Beams and columns are safe

Designing

During the preliminary design-stage the estimated external load is used to design the size and geometry of the structures of interconnected members by using local building code and specifications of the area where the structure is located. Therefore, assuring the structural integrity, durability etc. Neglecting this crucial design stage or erring during the process will result in catastrophic failure within the building structure which can, in the worst-case scenario may lead to the loss of lives. Since this stage is the most important, the margin of error is required to be close to zero.

CONCLUSION:

Analysis of a building ensures safety, serviceability, longevity and economic efficiency.

It can be done either by manually or with the help of automated computer software's.

The manual method of analyzing a building is time consuming and may result in various errors.

For this reason, we make use of computer software "E-TABS" which is efficient, reliable and precise.

With this study we like to conclude that through careful and precise analysis of buildings with the help of powerful computer software's the margin of error, the stability of the structure and an overall safe environment can be achieved.

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